

Interview - NetDRIVE Project

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

This document describes an interview undertaken as part of the context setting work. You can find a synthesis of all other interviews here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102198>

Interview: NetDRIVE

Meeting date: 12/03/2025

The Network for Sustainable Digital Research Infrastructure Vision and Expertise (NetDRIVE) has been set up to provide a forum for managers, software engineers, academics and others to come together to build a common vision for a sustainable future and to incite a transition to sustainable working practices in the Digital Research Infrastructure communities.

We spoke to one of the NetDRIVE project leads who has received 6 months of funding to write a proposal for NetDRIVE in a collaborative way, including a diverse range of users, DRI providers and community leaders.

Approach

- Community workshops: - presented 4 champions initially but shifted to a larger, more diverse team of champions working ~1 day a week - reaches larger group of people from within their institutions, going where networks exist already
 - This workshop led to a shift from problem focus 'here's a problem we'd like to solve' to people focus - who would be the best people for the role with leadership/network building experience, what would be in it for them in terms of skills and progression
- Inclusivity and diversity of perspectives has been valuable to building the project
- 1-to-1 discussions
- Keeping an eye on existing community discussions

- Summarised what they want to achieve on 1 slide - their 'elevator pitch'
 - Progress to cutting DRI emissions
 - UKRI contributing as a world-leader in the field
 - Building trust

Challenges

- Deficit in contributions from early career people - less likely to speak up in meetings
- Getting good engagement and actionable feedback in a limited time from a range of diverse backgrounds
- Everyone has their own ideas and problems which can be very different (especially gathered from a diverse audience) challenge to synthesize these and get from brainstorming > coalescing > recommendations
 - Managing contradictions and conflicts of ideas both a challenge and a positive thing to accept about working with diverse group - creating room for different views from people starting from different backgrounds
- Shifting views on behavioural change - it's about us not others! Keeping the idea present without it being an anxiety
- Managing multiple streams of work
- The need and benefit of being flexible poses challenges for the individuals working on the project
- Stigma associated with reaching out to social sciences, not necessarily built into work patterns at institutions (e.g. were able to hire a social scientist via the geography dept. instead of physics dept. to fit best with the institution)

What they have found from approach

- Diversity - requires resisting going down one track and keeping an open mind
- It's ok to accept contradictions and conflicts of ideas that come naturally from working with diverse group
- Focus on understanding how you will get measurable impact from the work, with target of immediate progress
- Really need people on board from the start - to address tight timescales, knowing that there are people who will engage and are familiar with the goals of the project
- The 'hook' from their project was clear:
 - People care about sustainability
 - People care about what their job will look like in the future and what they might be asked to do (in terms of DRI use) - want to be involved in that process
- Building trust:
 - meant people felt represented
 - Being open - e.g. making proposal public, having NERC presence at meetings shows interest from the top
 - Being flexible
 - Engaging with social scientists - evaluating where you've got trust is difficult!